

Robust Energy-Efficient Power Control and Beam-forming in Network Flooding

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Abstract—In a device-to-device wireless multi-hop communication scenario with resource-constrained devices, energy efficiency of communication plays a huge role. Based on the recently proposed Glossy network flooding protocol, we tackle the problem of robust multicast beamforming with imperfect CSI, and analyze its performance. The effect of number of CSI feedback bits B from receiving nodes to transmitting nodes on energy efficiency is investigated. Numerical simulations show that there exists an optimal number of feedback bits that maximizes energy efficiency. The programming problem for finding optimal B is formulated for a maximum allowed outage of 5% and the effect that has on energy efficiency is studied. Results show that higher outage requirements result in larger values of optimal number of feedback bits B for maximum energy efficiency.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent 5G initiatives have a clear focus on energy efficient smart cooperative transmission protocols [1]. Furthermore, cooperation in wireless networks is a topic that has attracted the attention of researchers for many years [2]–[5]. These initiatives are partially motivated by the importance of energy efficiency in large-scale wireless networks for internet of things (IoT) and cyber-physical systems applications [6]. Optimizing energy will help extend the expected lifetime of small battery operated devices such as sensor nodes, and facilitate their large scale deployment. To this end, we continue from [7] where a device-to-device wireless multi-hop communication scenario with resource-constrained devices that require energy-efficient connectivity is considered. Based on the recently proposed Glossy network flooding protocol [8], the beam-forming and power control problem is formulated, analyzed and assessed in network scenarios. Performance measures are compared, where the use of beamforming has proven to improve energy efficiency significantly.

In this work we consider the more practical scenario where the cost of cooperation in terms of energy consumption is taken into account. This cost of cooperation in our study is represented by the energy consumed in the process of channel state information (CSI) feedback from receiving to transmitting nodes. We note that there are several other factors that participate in this overhead in actual implementations of distributed multicast beamforming [9]. This results in a clear trade-off between complexity and energy efficiency [10].

After defining our problem in Section I-A, we present our system model in Section II. Following that, we formulate in Section III-A our general robust multicast beamforming problem, building therefore upon the results presented in [7]. Then, we show and discuss the effect of increasing feedback bits B on energy efficiency in Section III-B through simulation results and how the robust beamforming problem can be solved for application specific requirements. Numerical simulation results are illustrated in Section IV. Finally, we present our conclusions and agenda for future works in Section V.

A. Problem Statement

In order to efficiently manage network resources and achieve high energy efficiency in state-of-the-art Glossy [11], [12], we seek to analyze the feasibility of using power control and transmission cooperation schemes such as coherent multicast beamforming. To achieve our goal, we first look at the problem of limited feedback, where receiving nodes try to share their CSI with transmitting nodes using B feedback bits. Increasing the number of feedback bits B used in CSI sharing results in a better representation of the channels and lower quantization error. However, the consumed energy overhead by reliably transmitting these feedback bits increases as well. This results in a clear trade-off between the cooperation gain achieved by coherent multicast beamforming amongst the K transmitting nodes and the consumed energy overhead due to CSI feedback. Therefore, there must exist an optimal B^* , dependent on network parameters such as topology, number of transmitters K and density of the network, that maximizes energy efficiency.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In order to examine the effect of limited feedback on a complex communication scenario such as Glossy, we must first consider the general single hop case where K transmitting single-antenna-nodes are cooperating to send the same encoded data symbol x to L receiving nodes using multi-cast beam-forming. The signal received at receiver l is mathematically described as

$$y_l = \mathbf{h}_l \mathbf{w} x + z_l \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{w} is a beamforming vector, $\mathbf{h}_1, \mathbf{h}_2, \dots, \mathbf{h}_L$ are the channel vectors of receivers 1 to L and $\mathbf{h}_l = [h_{1l}, h_{2l}, \dots, h_{Kl}]$

Figure 1: Our system model consisting of K transmitting nodes and L receiving nodes. Feedback channels FB_l are considered to be error-free.

where $h_{kl} \in \mathbb{C}$ is the channel gain from transmitter k to receiver l modeled as quasi-static, independent, and experience flat-fading on the block length, which is a valid assumption for low-power wireless devices. These coefficients are calculated according to $h_{kl} = w_{kl}g_{kl}$, where small-scale fading w_{kl} follows a complex normal distribution $\mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$, and large-scale fading g_{kl} depends on the distance d_{kl} between transmitter k and receiver l [13, E 5.3] as follows

$$g_{kl} = \begin{cases} 40.2 + 20 \log(d_{kl}) & , d_{kl} \leq 8 \text{ m} \\ 58.5 + 33 \log(d_{kl}/8) & , d_{kl} > 8 \text{ m} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

which corresponds to a path loss exponent of 2 for the first 8 m and a path loss exponent of 3.3 for distances larger than 8 m. To ensure $g_{kl} > 0$ according to (2), we consider only topologies where the distance between any pair of nodes exceeds 0.1 m, which is reasonable in real deployments [14]. We denote the normalized channel vector $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l = \frac{\mathbf{h}_l}{\|\mathbf{h}_l\|}$, where $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l$ is a unit vector that describes only the channel direction. Moreover, in our model, transmitters are assumed to know the channel quality information (CQI), represented by $\|\mathbf{h}_l\|$, perfectly. Finally, z_l is additive white Gaussian noise with a complex normal distribution $z_l \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_l^2)$.

Each receiver l is assumed to know local CSI \mathbf{h}_l , this can be done through pilot training [15], [16] at the beginning of transmission and is not the focus of this work. CSI is then quantized and shared with transmitting nodes through a limited feedback channel as described in Section II-A and Section II-B.

A. Random Vector Quantization

Quantization is done using randomly generated vector quantization codebooks independently at each receiver. A code book \mathcal{C} contains 2^B K -dimensional unit norm vectors randomly drawn from the isotropic distribution on the K -dimensional unit sphere where $\mathcal{C} \triangleq \{\mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_2, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{2^B}\}$. In addition to being mathematically tractable, RVQ performs close to optimal quantization as feedback bits $B \rightarrow \infty$ [17]. This can be independently applied at each receiver l where the closest vector \mathbf{u}_i to the normalized real channel $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l$ is chosen. The index i is then broadcasted to active transmitters using

B feedback bits. This will be described in more details later on in Section II-B. Now we direct our attention towards the RVQ process where the closest vector \mathbf{u}_i to the normalized real channel $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l$ has to be chosen. we adopt two different definitions of closeness, each with merits and drawbacks. First, we consider the same measure as in [18], where closeness is defined as the absolute value of the inner product of the two vectors \mathbf{u}_i and $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l$, in other words, the angle between them. Then, we consider the Euclidean distance, defined as the norm of the difference between \mathbf{u}_i and $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l$, as a measure of closeness. This is explained in more details in the following **Minimum Angle**. Each receiver must choose the closest vector \mathbf{u}_i to the normalized channel $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l$ independently. This is done by solving the following problem [18]

$$i = \arg \max_{1 \leq i \leq 2^B} |\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l^H \mathbf{u}_i|^2 \quad (3)$$

where $\Upsilon = \max_{1 \leq i \leq 2^B} |\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l^H \mathbf{u}_i|^2$ is the maximum of 2^N beta distributed random variables with $(\alpha = 1, \beta = K - 1)$, $\beta(\alpha, \beta)$ is the normal beta function with parameters α and β , and i is the index corresponding to the closest vector to the normalized channel $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l$ in code book \mathcal{C} such that $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^\theta = \mathbf{u}_i$ is the quantized channel vector based on the angle. This index has to be then transmitted to the transmitters. From [19] Lemma 1, the CDF of Υ is given by

$$\Pr(\Upsilon \leq v) = (1 - v^{(K-1)})^{2^B} \quad (4)$$

The quantization error vector, defined as the difference between normalized channel vector $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l$ and quantized channel vector $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^\theta$, can be described as $\delta_\theta = \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l - \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^\theta$, and therefore the norm of the error vector can be calculated as

$$\|\delta_\theta\|^2 = \|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l - \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^\theta\|^2 \quad (5)$$

where we emphasize the fact that here, the vector $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l$ is chosen based on the angle. Then, the square of the norm of the error becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \|\delta_\theta\|^2 &= (\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l - \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^\theta)^H (\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l - \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^\theta) \\ &= \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l^H \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l - \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l^H \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^\theta - \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l^H \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^\theta + \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^{\theta H} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^\theta \\ &= 2 - 2 \operatorname{Re}\{\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l^H \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^\theta\} \\ &= 2 \left(1 - |\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l^H \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^\theta| \cos(\angle \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l^H, \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^\theta)\right) \\ &= 2 \left(1 - \sqrt{\Upsilon} \cos(U)\right) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where U is a random variable representing the angle between normalized channel vector $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l$ and quantized channel vector $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^\theta$. This angle is isotropic and uniformly distributed from $-\pi$ to π because of the randomness of codebook \mathcal{C} . The Probability Density Function (PDF) of $Y = \cos(U)$ is given by

$$\Pr(Y \leq y) = \frac{1}{\pi \sqrt{1 - y^2}} \quad (7)$$

Figure 2: Comparison between approximated CDF of $\|\delta_\theta\|^2$ based on minimizing the angle, and empirical CDF of $\|\delta_d\|^2$ for different values of B based on minimizing the norm of the error vector

We substitute $G = \sqrt{Y}Y$. Therefore, the CDF of the error can be calculated using a simple change of variables and the approximation derived in Appendix A as

$$\Pr(\|\delta_\theta\|^2 \leq \epsilon^2) \approx \frac{1}{2} + \frac{\arcsin(\frac{\epsilon^2}{2} - 1)}{\pi} \quad (8)$$

where ϵ^2 is defined on the interval $(0, 4)$. While this closed form expression for the CDF is very useful in analytically solving our problem, choosing the quantized channel vector based on the angle does not result in minimizing the norm of the quantization error $\|\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l - \mathbf{u}_i\|^2$. Therefore, we introduce another way to choose the quantized channel vector $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l$ based on the minimum Euclidean distance.

Minimum Euclidean Distance. Each receiver must choose the closest vector \mathbf{u}_i to the normalized channel $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l$ independently. This is done by solving the following problem

$$i = \arg \min_{1 \leq i \leq 2^B} \|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l - \mathbf{u}_i\|^2 \quad (9)$$

Since the quantization error vector is described in the same way as before, the norm of the error vector is

$$\|\delta_d\|^2 = \|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l - \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l\|^2 \quad (10)$$

where here the $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l$ is the quantized channel vector based on the euclidean distance. This manner of choosing the quantized channel vector results in the minimum error norm possible. However, the CDF of this error is not available in closed form. The CDF of $\|\delta_d\|^2$ can be seen in Figure 2 for both methods. It is clear that the first method results in higher values of $\|\delta_\theta\|^2$ than the second. It is important to note that from (5) and (10), $\delta_\theta \neq \delta_d$ because the index i resulting from (3) is not necessarily equal to the index i resulting from (9).

B. Feedback Overhead

Thanks to the broadcast nature of the wireless medium and assuming error free feedback channels, it is safe to assume that a signal received successfully by the furthest transmitter can be received by all other transmitters and the power needed for reliable transmission is

$$P_l = (2^B - 1) \max_{1 \leq j \leq K, j \neq l} |d_{lj}|^2 \quad (11)$$

where d_{lj} is the distance from receiver l to transmitter j , operator $|\cdot|$ denotes the Euclidean norm and P_l is defined as the transmission power needed to distribute CSI from receiver l to all transmitters. The total feedback overhead is defined as

$$P_{coop} = (2^B - 1) \sum_{l=1}^L \max_{1 \leq j \leq K, j \neq l} |d_{lj}|^2 \quad (12)$$

where we can see the dependency of P_{coop} exponentially on the number of feedback bits B and linearly on the distances between receivers and transmitters. This means that increasing the number of feedback bits B will result in a higher cooperation overhead in terms of P_{coop} , but will also result in a more accurate quantization of the channels, leading to less transmit power. Therefore, there must be an optimum number of feedback bits B that minimizes total energy consumption and maximizes energy efficiency.

III. ROBUST BEAMFORMING

A. Transmit Beamforming Optimization

In our previous work [7] we have considered the case of multicast beamforming under the assumption of perfect CSI available at both transmitter and receiver. The following programming problem was solved for the optimal beamformer \mathbf{W}

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize} && \text{tr}(\mathbf{W}) \\ & \text{subject to} && \mathbf{h}_l \mathbf{W} \mathbf{h}_l^H \geq (2^R - 1) \sigma_l^2; \forall l \in \mathcal{L} \\ & && \mathbf{W} \succeq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where the inequality $\mathbf{W} \succeq 0$ means that \mathbf{W} is a symmetric positive semidefinite matrix that is greater than or equal to zero in the lowner order. The programming problem in (13) is a convex problem with a linear objective function, convex constraint set and is formulated as explained in [2]. To solve this problem, we use CVX, a Matlab package for solving convex programs [20], [21].

Unfortunately perfect CSI knowledge at the transmitter side is not always possible. Therefore based on the available CSI provided to the transmitters through limited feedback and using the uncertainty model explained in Section II-A, the transmitter has to estimate the real channels in order to calculate the appropriate beamformer. First, in order to satisfy the QoS constraints at each receiver l the following must hold

$$\log \left(1 + \frac{\mathbf{h}_l \mathbf{W} \mathbf{h}_l^H}{\sigma_l^2} \right) \geq R; \forall l \in \mathcal{L} \quad (14)$$

The real channel \mathbf{h}_l can be written in terms of the quantized channel direction $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l$ and the error as such

$$\mathbf{h}_l = \|\mathbf{h}_l\| \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l = \|\mathbf{h}_l\| (\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l + \delta) \quad (15)$$

Please note that both $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l$ and $\|\mathbf{h}_l\|$ are known by the transmitter. Therefore, after some algebraic manipulations, (14) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} (\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l + \delta) \mathbf{W} (\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l + \delta)^H &\geq \frac{(2^R - 1)\sigma_l^2}{\|\mathbf{h}_l\|^2}; \\ \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall \delta : \|\delta\| &\leq \epsilon \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $\delta \leq \epsilon$ is an upper bound on the norm of quantization error. In order to design a beam-former that is robust against quantization error, the transmitters must minimize the transmit power while satisfying the rate constraints in (16). Using (16) and (13), the robust beam-forming optimization problem can be formulated as follows

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{minimize } tr(\mathbf{W}) \\ &\text{subject to } (\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l + \delta) \mathbf{W} (\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l + \delta)^H \geq \frac{(2^R - 1)\sigma_l^2}{\|\mathbf{h}_l\|^2}; \\ &\quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall \delta : \|\delta\| \leq \epsilon \\ &\quad \mathbf{W} \succeq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Since the quantization error vector δ is random and exact knowledge of its direction is not available at the transmitter, we try to modify the optimization problem mathematically so it can be solved numerically. To that purpose, we apply some simplification and algebraic modifications to the constraints in (16) similar to the analysis done in [22]. The robust beam-forming optimization problem in (17) becomes equivalent to the following semi definite programming problem which can be solved by software defined tools [20], [21]

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{minimize } tr(\mathbf{W}) \\ &\text{subject to } \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l (\mathbf{W} - \mathbf{Q}) \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^H - \epsilon^2 \mu \geq \frac{(2^R - 1)\sigma_l^2}{\|\mathbf{h}_l\|^2}; \\ &\quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \mu \geq 0, \mathbf{W} \succeq 0 \\ &\quad \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q} & \mathbf{W} \\ \mathbf{W} & \mathbf{W} + \mu \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Based on S-procedure and Schur Complement as explained in appendices B and C, respectively, we first transform the rate constraints in (16) as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \mathbf{W} \delta^H + 2\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \mathbf{W} \delta^H + \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \mathbf{W} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^H - z &\geq 0; \\ \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \forall \delta : -\|\delta\|^2 + \epsilon^2 &\geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where $z = \frac{(2^R - 1)\sigma_l^2}{\|\mathbf{h}_l\|^2}$, and $\|\delta\|^2 = \delta^H \delta$. According to S-Procedure, this holds if and only if there exists $\mu \geq 0$ such that

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W} + \mu \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{W} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \\ \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \mathbf{W} & \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \mathbf{W} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^H - \epsilon^2 \mu - z \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0, \quad (20)$$

This provides us with 2 separate cases for μ . First, we examine the case where $\mu > 0$. Using Schur Complement, (20) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \mathbf{W} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^H - \epsilon^2 \mu - z - \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \mathbf{W} [\mathbf{W} + \mu \mathbf{I}]^{-1} \mathbf{W} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^H &\geq 0 \\ \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \mathbf{W} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^H - \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \mathbf{W} [\mathbf{W} + \mu \mathbf{I}]^{-1} \mathbf{W} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^H - \epsilon^2 \mu &\geq z \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Second, we introduce \mathbf{Q} , where $\mathbf{Q} \succeq [\mathbf{W} + \mu \mathbf{I}]^{-1} \mathbf{W}$. The robust beam-forming optimization problem in (17) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{minimize } tr(\mathbf{W}) \\ &\text{subject to } \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \mathbf{W} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^H - \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \mathbf{Q} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^H - \epsilon^2 \mu \geq \frac{(2^R - 1)\sigma_l^2}{\|\mathbf{h}_l\|^2}; \\ &\quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \mu > 0, \mathbf{W} \succeq 0 \\ &\quad \mathbf{Q} - [\mathbf{W} + \mu \mathbf{I}]^{-1} \mathbf{W} \succeq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

By applying Schur Complement to the constraint in (22), it can be transformed equivalently into

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{minimize } tr(\mathbf{W}) \\ &\text{subject to } \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l (\mathbf{W} - \mathbf{Q}) \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^H - \epsilon^2 \mu \geq \frac{(2^R - 1)\sigma_l^2}{\|\mathbf{h}_l\|^2}; \\ &\quad \forall l \in \mathcal{L}, \mu > 0, \mathbf{W} \succeq 0 \\ &\quad \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q} & \mathbf{W} \\ \mathbf{W} & \mathbf{W} + \mu \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Second, for $\mu = 0$, (20) amounts to

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W} & \mathbf{W} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \\ \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \mathbf{W} & \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \mathbf{W} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^H - z \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0 \quad (24)$$

and equivalently

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^H & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W} & \mathbf{W} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \\ \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \mathbf{W} & \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \mathbf{W} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_l^H - z \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} -\hat{\mathbf{h}}_l \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = -z \geq 0 \quad (25)$$

which means that the constraints in (23) can be satisfied for the case of $\mu = 0$ by having $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{W}$ and can hereby be included into (23), arriving to the final result in (18).

B. Feedback Optimization

With the use of simplified system level simulations in Section IV, we evaluate and study the effect that number of feedback bits B has on energy efficiency of an arbitrary single hop within a Glossy flood. This is the first step towards the optimization of feedback bits B from an energy efficiency point of view. First, we must define our performance measures. So we begin by defining energy efficiency as follows

$$EE = \frac{\text{Rate}}{\text{Total energy consumption}} \quad (26)$$

where the rate is defined as the successfully received rate at each receiver, and the total energy consumption is the sum of transmit energies for all transmitters and the cooperation overhead P_{coop} as defined in (12). Then the energy efficiency can be rewritten as such

$$EE = \frac{(1 - \text{Pr}_o)R}{tr(\mathbf{W}) + P_{coop}} \quad (27)$$

where Pr_o is the outage probability.

Figure 3: Expected reception ratio based on CDF of $\|\delta\|^2$ and actual reception ratio after solving the robust beamforming optimization problem.

Figure 4: Energy efficiency in Kbit/Joule evaluated at different values of feedback bits B for $K = 4, 5$ and $L = 1$

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

We generate network topologies using a binomial point process with $\lambda = k + L$ nodes randomly and independently deployed. We then evaluate energy efficiency using robust multicast beamforming for different values of feedback bits B . Our results are averaged over 500 independent realizations of the network for the same λ . Irrespective of the topology, all transmitting nodes have a source rate $R = 250$ kbps which corresponds to the default setting as prescribed by the IEEE 802.15.4 standard. The first step to optimizing the system is solving the programming problem in (18). After that, we move on to choose the number of feedback bits B that maximizes energy efficiency. This is shown together with system level simulations in Section IV-A and Section IV-B.

A. Tightness of bounds

The programming problem in (18) is designed to minimize transmit power under QoS constraints. However, minimizing transmit power does not always mean an increase in energy efficiency. Other factors affect energy efficiency such as outage probability and feedback overhead P_{coop} which can be seen in (27). Modifying the optimization problem depends on

the reliability requirements of the application. For example, in critical applications, an upper bound on the outage is needed. Therefore, we use the CDF of $\|\delta\|^2$ as described in (8) where outage probability is upper bounded as such $\Pr_o \leq \Pr(\|\delta\|^2 > \epsilon^2)$ and we solve for $\epsilon(B, K)$. This bound can not be described as a tight bound because of the random direction of δ , which can result in a better or worse quantized channel $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l$ than the real channel \mathbf{h}_l . Using this approach will result in over satisfying the reliability requirements, hence losing some energy efficiency. However, the system can be solved for different number of feedback bits B and ultimately find the optimum B^* that maximizes energy efficiency, while maintaining a maximum outage probability \Pr_o . The tightness of our bound can be seen in Figure 3, where the reception ratio resulting from solving our robust optimization problem in (18) is calculated for different values of ϵ^2 . This is compared in the same plot with the CDF of $\|\delta\|^2$ for the simulation scenario of $K = 3$ and $B = 4$. It is critical here to emphasize the relationship between the CDF of ϵ^2 and the reception ratio. Assuming we use an ϵ^2 corresponding to a 90% in the CDF, this means that 90% of the square of the quantization error norm is indeed below this value, in turn, resulting in a successful reception 90% of the time. However, It is easy to notice that achieving 90% reception ratio requires a smaller ϵ^2 than the one retrieved from the CDF information available at the transmitter. This bound can be tightened further by means of iterated optimization, where instead of minimizing $\|\delta\|^2$ we minimize $\delta^H \mathbf{W} \delta$. This results in recursively choosing a quantized channel $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_l$ and a beamformer \mathbf{W} that further maximize energy efficiency under rate constraints. We leave this approach for future works, and we direct our focus to optimizing number of feedback bits B .

B. Feasibility and Optimality

After fixing an upper limit of on the outage probability to $\Pr_o = 5\%$, the corresponding ϵ_o^2 can be calculated by means of numerical search. Using this value, the programming problem in (18) can be solved for the minimum transmit power. However, our goal is to maximize energy efficiency. Therefore, the following optimization problem must be solved.

$$\max_B \frac{(1 - \Pr_o) R}{\text{tr}(\mathbf{W}) + P_{coop}} \quad (28)$$

where \mathbf{W} can be calculated by numerically solving the programming problem in (18) for $\epsilon^2 = \epsilon_o^2$

As can be seen in Figure 4, the energy efficiency of the single hop multicast communication depends on the number of feedback bits B . In the considered scenario in Figure 4, the optimum B for the case of $K = 5$ and $K = 4$ is 5 and 4 bits, respectively. This is a result of needing less total transmit power to satisfy rate constraints when increasing the number of transmitters K , while the overhead of cooperation is independent of K . It is important to note that the choice of ϵ_o , in this scenario, is done using numerical search. This is done off-line and stored at each transmitter, which is not very practical and dynamic. However, this problem can indeed be

formulating a closed form expression or an approximation of the quantization error estimate, which will be studied in future works.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

We have studied the problem of robust multicast beamforming in Glossy under imperfect CSI and limited feedback. It was shown that coherent multicast beamforming, can lead to significant gains in terms of energy efficiency. By studying the effect of number of feedback bits B on the performance, we show that there exists an optimal B that maximizes energy efficiency. Moreover, the problem was solved for a specific maximum allowed outage probability. The results show that stricter outage requirements, result in higher values of optimal B^* . The upper bound used on the outage probability can be tightened using iterative beamforming, resulting in lower transmit power while still satisfying the rate constraints. However, we leave this to be investigated later on in a future extension to this work.

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APPENDIX A

CUMULATIVE DISTRIBUTION FUNCTION

Assuming we have two independent random variables X and Y , such that the probability distribution functions of X and Y are given by $f_X(x)$ and $f_Y(y)$, respectively. where

$$F_X(x) = \left[1 - (1 - x^2)^{K-1}\right]^{2B} \text{ where } 0 \leq x \leq 1 \quad (29)$$

is the cumulative distribution function of X . and

$$f_Y(y) = \frac{1}{\pi\sqrt{1-y^2}} \text{ where } -1 < y < 1 \quad (30)$$

is the probability density function of Y . The cumulative distribution function of $Z = XY$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} F_Z(z) &= \int_{-\infty}^z \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{x} f_X(x) f_Y\left(\frac{w}{x}\right) dx dw \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^z \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{x} \frac{d}{dx} F_X(x) f_Y\left(\frac{w}{x}\right) dx dw \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

by applying integration by parts and considering that Z is defined on the interval $(-1, 1)$, (31) can be rewritten as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_Z(z) &= \int_{-1}^z \frac{1}{x} F_X(x) f_Y\left(\frac{w}{x}\right) \Big|_{-\infty}^{\infty} dw - \\
 &\quad \int_{-1}^z \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{x} F_X(x) \frac{d}{dx} f_Y\left(\frac{w}{x}\right) dx dw \\
 &= \int_{-1}^z \frac{1}{\pi \sqrt{x^2 - w^2}} \left(1 - (1 - x^2)^{K-1}\right)^{2B} \Big|_0^1 dw - \\
 &\quad \int_{-1}^z \int_0^1 \frac{1}{x} F_X(x) \frac{d}{dx} f_Y\left(\frac{w}{x}\right) dx dw \\
 &= \int_{-1}^z \frac{1}{\pi \sqrt{1 - w^2}} dw - \\
 &\quad \int_{-1}^z \int_0^1 \frac{1}{x} F_X(x) \frac{d}{dx} f_Y\left(\frac{w}{x}\right) dx dw \\
 &= \frac{\arcsin(z)}{\pi} + \frac{1}{2} - \int_{-1}^z \int_0^1 \frac{1}{x} F_X(x) \frac{d}{dx} f_Y\left(\frac{w}{x}\right) dx dw
 \end{aligned} \tag{32}$$

where the complexity of the remaining integral is very high such that it can not be solved even with numerical methods. The CDF of Z can be then approximated to

$$F_Z(z) = \frac{\arcsin(z)}{\pi} + \frac{1}{2} \tag{33}$$

The accuracy of this approximation can be seen in Figure 5 where the error decreases by increasing $B > K$.

Figure 5: Comparison between approximated and empirical CDF of Z for different values of B . Error in the approximation decreases by increasing B

APPENDIX B S-PROCEDURE

The S-Procedure gives conditions under which, a particular quadratic inequality is a consequence of another quadratic inequality [23].

Let \mathbf{A}_1 and \mathbf{A}_2 be symmetric matrices, \mathbf{b}_1 and \mathbf{b}_2 be vectors, and c_1 and c_2 are constants. Assuming there exists some \mathbf{x} such that

$$\mathbf{x}^H \mathbf{A}_1 \mathbf{x} + 2\mathbf{b}_1 \mathbf{x} + c_1 \geq 0 \tag{34}$$

then the following holds

$$\mathbf{x}^H \mathbf{A}_2 \mathbf{x} + 2\mathbf{b}_2 \mathbf{x} + c_2 \geq 0 \tag{35}$$

if and only if there exists a $\mu \geq 0$, such that

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_2 & \mathbf{b}_2 \\ \mathbf{b}_2^H & c_2 \end{bmatrix} - \mu \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_1 & \mathbf{b}_1 \\ \mathbf{b}_1^H & c_1 \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0 \tag{36}$$

APPENDIX C SCHUR COMPLEMENT

The Schur complement is defined as follows. Assume having

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{C} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \succeq 0 \tag{37}$$

where $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}$, and \mathbf{D} are matrices, and \mathbf{D} is invertible. Then, the Schur complement of \mathbf{D} in M is

$$\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{D}^{-1}\mathbf{C} \succeq 0 \tag{38}$$

However, If \mathbf{A} is invertible, then the Schur complement of \mathbf{A} in M is

$$\mathbf{D} - \mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{B} \succeq 0 \tag{39}$$